

(Effects of Three-Pair-Strategy using VARK Model on Performance ... Abdulmalik, L., Et. al. 2025)

Effects of Three-Pair-Strategy using VARK Model on Performance and Retention in Electrolysis among Senior Secondary School Students in Zamfara State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

The study assessed the Effect of Three Pair Strategy on Academic Performance and Retention in Electrolysis among Senior Secondary Schools two (SS2) students, Two research questions and two null hypothesis guided the study, The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design The population was 25,335 from 189 public schools SS2 students offering chemistry in Zamfara State. A sample of 70 students drawn from 2 schools was selected using multi-stage sampling techniques by balloting, One instrument was used for data collection Electrolysis Performance Test (EPT) .The instrument was subjected to content validity by three experts which are senior lecturers, two from Department of Science Education and from Measurement and evaluation Faculty of Education Federal University Gusau., and the Reliability coefficient of 0.87 using Test-retest was obtained during the pilot study, The pretest and posttest was used for data collection, Descriptive statistics of mean was used to answer the research questions while standard deviation was adopted to a certain the homogeneity or other wise of the respondents performance scores. Inferential statistics of analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the formulated hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. Finding of the study revealed that three pair strategy significantly enhanced performance and retention scores of SS2 students in electrolysis more than discussion method. Base of this finding the study recommended amongst others that the Zamfara state ministry of education should organized seminary, workshops and conferences for teachers most especially chemistry teachers on how to uses three pair strategy in teaching electrolysis.

keywords: electrolysis, academic performance, retention, three pair strategy,

Introduction

Science education refers to the process of teaching and learning science in formal and informal educational setting, science Education is aimed at inculcating in the learner appropriate skills to live in and contribute to the development of the society. Science is a very important aspect in the development of any nation and is regarded as instrument per excellence for solving socio-economic

(Effects of Three-Pair-Strategy using VARK Model on Performance ... Abdulmalik, L., Et. al. 2025)

problem of various kinds (Ghumdia, 2017) science has helped to meet the minimum needs of human in the society in terms of food, shelter, clothing, water, unemployment, basic education, transportation, communication and health care (Ongowo, 2017). Despite the roles played by science in the society some students still display negative attitudes toward the study of nature of some topics in science subject (Adegboye, and Samba, 2017) Science education encompasses a broad range of topics, which chemistry is part of them,

Chemistry as a core science subject required in all science secondary school in Nigeria and a subject requirement for admission in to science field of study in tertiary institution. Chemistry as a branch of science and the prerequisite subject for many fields of learning contributes immensely to the technological growth of the nation. This includes medicine, forestry, agriculture, pharmacy, laboratory science, biochemistry, biotechnology and nursing. The study of chemistry in senior secondary school can equipped students with useful concepts, principles, laws fact and theories that would enables them face the challenges before and after graduation (Victor and Aondofa 2024).

Despite the importance of chemistry and specifically Concept Electrolysis and the efforts of researchers on teaching and learning shows that academic performance of students in the chemistry remains poor in Nigeria. This poor academic performance is attested to by (Victor and Aondofa 2024) that students' performance in chemistry is relatively poor especially in some aspect of chemistry such as electrolysis, thermodynamics and so on. Some of the identified problems according to (Atsuwe, and Nyinya, 2022), include Science education faces numerous obstacles, including passive teaching, inadequate teacher quality, poor work environment, insufficient laboratory facilities, low teacher morale, and inadequate research funding.

Furthermore, (Akpghol, Samba, and Asemave, 2020) Stated poor teaching method is a major cause of students' poor academic performance in chemistry. Hence, the implication of the persistent poor academic performance in chemistry is that the much-needed educational development will remain a wishful thinking until the inherent problems are identified and remedied. Therefore, if chemistry especially concept of electrolysis is properly taught using effective and appropriate strategies, students' academic performance could be enhanced and therefore provide the nation with valuable technological development, which are required for the achievement of both personal and national goals. According to (Ajayi and Audu 2023) Teachers should adopt diverse instructional methods beyond traditional approaches, as students' mastery of a subject is crucial for their success in examinations.

The three pair instructional strategy is a collaborative learning approach that aims to promote critical thinking, problems solving and effective communication among students. Johnson and Johnson (2009) noted that students who used the three pair strategy showed significant gains in achievement and engagement compared to those who used traditional teaching methods, like wise Gilles and Ashmen (2003) laid that the three pair strategy improved students' ability to work collaboratively, where ideas and build on each other's thinking. In a study conducted by joyce and showers (2002) found that teachers who received professional development on the three pair strategy showed significance improvements in their instructional practice and students' outcomes. Hmelo-silver (2004). Demonstrated that teachers who used the three pair strategy reported increased confidence and

(Effects of Three-Pair-Strategy using VARK Model on Performance ... Abdulmalik, L., Et. al. 2025)

competence in their ability to promote collaborative learning. In a study conducted by Tomlinson (2001); the study found that the three pair strategy was effective in promoting learning and engagement among diverse learners. Student with disabilities and English language learners. Gay (2000) laid that, the three pair strategy helped to create an inclusive classroom environment that valued diversity and promoted social justice. These studies provide evidence that the three pair instructional strategy can be an effective approach to promoting students' achievement, engagement and social skills as well as teacher professional development inclusive classroom.

The VARK model is an acronym that stands for (visual, auditory, read/write, and kinesthetic), It was introduced by Neil Fleming in (1987). He observed over '1999' classroom lessons, and those observations led him to develop the VARK model which, according to Fleming refers to "the category of instructional preference because it deals with perceptual modes". The VARK model is based on Neuro-Linguistic Programming ideology (NLP) which is "a name that encompasses the three most influential components involved in producing human experience: neurology, language and programming" The VARK also addresses the human perceptual modes and senses except for the smell and taste senses. "VARK above all is designed to be a starting place for a conversation among teachers and learners about learning. It can also be a catalyst for staff development- thinking about strategies for teaching different groups of learners can lead to more, and appropriate, variety of learning and teaching". Indeed, learners can learn by more than one method, but it does not mean they have no preference for a specific learning style.

Performance can be explained as a term which is directly proportional to change in a learning context, input, or classroom process. performance therefore simply means the extent to which a student, a teacher or an institution has reached its educational goal.it is commonly measured by examinations or other means of evaluation of teaching and learning outcome. Sati (2014) described performance as a complex student's behavior that's underlies several abilities, examples include memory, previous knowledge, as well as psychological factors like motivation, interest, temperament or emotion. Jiya (2011) states that literally, the ability to store and remember ideas and facts is term as retention. Ochonnogor (2014) wrote that retention can be measured through verbal recall of learnt materials, and explained that concepts learnt assist in reflective thinking and that trained concepts can be used in creative ways to solve new problems.

Few studies were found to investigate the Effect of Three Pair Strategy on Performance and Retention in Electrolysis. Therefore, this study aimed to investigate the Effect of Three Pair Strategy using VARK model on Performance and Retention in Electrolysis among Senior Secondary School Students in Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Statement of The Problem

Ideally the teachers should demonstrate excellent and employed innovative strategy, leading to improved academic performance and preparedness for future study. For any meaningful learning to occur, there should be trained and qualified teachers employing appropriate instructional method. Available research findings showed that chemistry teachers in Nigerian secondary schools adopt

(Effects of Three-Pair-Strategy using VARK Model on Performance ... Abdulmalik, L., Et. al. 2025)

conventional lecture method of teaching chemistry concepts. Lack of personalized learning approaches insufficient consideration of individuals learning styles, limited student engagement and interaction, inadequate assessment and feedback mechanisms. (Ahiakwo and Ene, 2022).

The consistent decline in the performance and retention of chemistry students in most secondary schools in Nigeria is the major problem that prompted this investigation. According to WAEC Chief Examiner 2020 the senior secondary school candidate that register for senior school certificate Examination in Zamfara state only 22.22% passed chemistry at credit level. In 2021 the percentage passes at credit level increase to 44.05% in 2022 the percentage that pass at credit level dropped to 9.5%. While In 2023 Zamfara had the lowest performance at 39.10% followed by niger (46.87) and jigawa (49.63), in 2024 the percentage that pass at credit level dropped to 32,20%.

The implication if these problems were not addressed they will lead to poor academic performance in chemistry and related subject, difficulty in pursuing science related careers, limited understanding of essential concepts and long term consequences on science technology engineering and mathematic [STEM] education and innovation. Optimal chemistry learning outcomes require teachers to employ evidence-based instructional strategies that promote student engagement, motivation, and academic performance. (Ajaye and Audu 2024).

Objective of The Study

The specific objectives of this study are to:

- i. Determine the means performance scores of students taught electrolysis using three pairs strategy and those exposed to discussion method.
- ii. Examine the means retention scores of students taught electrolysis using three pairs strategy and those exposed to discussion method.

Research Questions

This study attempt to formulate two research questions for answering:

- i. What is the mean performance score of students taught electrolysis using three pair strategy and those exposed to discussion method?
- ii. What is the mean retention score of students taught electrolysis using three pair strategy and those exposed to discussion method?

Null Hypothesis

Based on the research questions raised, the following null hypothesis were formulated and tested at 0.05 significant level

H₀₁. There is no significant difference in mean performance score of students taught concepts electrolysis and those exposed to discussion method.

H₀₂ There is no significant difference in mean retention score of students taught concepts electrolysis and those exposed to discussion method.

Research Methodology

(Effects of Three-Pair-Strategy using VARK Model on Performance ... Abdulmalik, L., Et. al. 2025)

Quasi-experimental design was adopted for the study. Specifically, the pre-test posttest non-equivalent control group design was used. This research design is considered suitable because it allows the researcher to observe the performance and retention of students before and after manipulations of the independent variable. The population of this study comprises 25,335 SS2 chemistry students in Zamfara State. Sample size for this study is 70 SS 2 chemistry students. Multi-stage sampling procedure was used to compose the sample which involves purposive and simple random sampling technique using balloting. From the experimental school, the intact class of 38 (24 males and 14 females) was used and from the control school, an intact class of 32 (21 males and 11 females) was used. The instrument used for data collection was Electrolysis Performance Test (EPT). This was composed by the researcher using WAEC past question papers for 4 years (2020, 2021, 2022 and 2023). The research instrument EPT is made up of 30 multiple choice objective test items with four options, A, B, C, and D which covers the content electrolysis. The researcher used the instrument during the pre-test and the same was used for post-test. This instrument was reshuffled again and used as retention test. The content validity was used to ensure the validity of the instrument by three experts; two from the Department of Science Education and one from measurement and Evaluation, Faculty of education Federal University Gusau. In order to ascertain the level to which EPT was reliable' Test-retest method was used to statistically estimate the internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Data thus collected from the pilot study were analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient of 0.87, Data obtained were analyzed with the descriptive statistics of mean to answer the research questions while standard deviation was used to ascertain the homogeneity or otherwise of the respondents' Performance scores. Inferential statistics of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 alpha level. The null hypothesis was rejected if probability value is less than or equal to the significant value of 0.05 ($P \leq 0.05$) and if otherwise ($P > 0.05$), it was accepted.

Presentation of Results

Table 1: Difference between the Mean performance scores of SS 2 students taught Electrolysis using three pair instructional strategy and discussion Method

Group	N	Pretest	Posttest	Mean gain	Mean difference
Experimental (three pair strategy)	38	35.45	71.07	32.67	3.29
Control (discussion method)	32	21.51	50.89	29.38	

Table 1: shows that the mean performance scores of students taught with three pair strategy is higher than those taught using the discussion method because the gain in mean of 32.67 for the experimental group is greater than 29.38 gain in mean for the control group. The mean difference is 3.29 in favour of experimental group.

(Effects of Three-Pair-Strategy using VARK Model on Performance ... Abdulmalik, L., Et. al. 2025)

Table 2: Difference between the mean retention scores of SS 2 students taught Electrolysis using three pair strategy and those taught using discussion method.

Group	N	Pre test	Retention test	Mean loss	Means difference
Experimental (three pair strategy)	38	71.07	68.12	-2.95	0.30
Control (discussion method)	32	50.89	42.64	-3.25	

Table 2: indicates a mean loss of 2.95 for students taught using three pair strategy and 3.25 for those taught using discussion method. This proves that students in the experimental group retained slightly higher than those in the control group. These differences in mean was tested for significance.

Table 3: ANCOVA test of significant difference between the mean performance scores of SS 2 students taught Electrolysis using three pair strategy and those taught using discussion method.

Source	Type III sum of squares	Df	Means square	F	Sig
Corrected model	1445.007	2	722.504	100.473	.000
Intercept	4369.875	1	4369.875	607.685	.000
Performance	.397	1	.397	.055	.815
Treatment	1308.402	1	1308.402	181.949	.000
Error	286.968	70	7.191		
Total	164629.000	71			
Corrected total	2271.975	69			

R square = 636 (adjusted R squared = 630)

Table3: reveal that the difference in the mean performance scores of SS 2 students taught Electrolysis using three pair strategy and those taught using discussion method is significant because the p-value of 0.000 is less than the alpha level of 0.05 at 70 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, thus, there is significant difference between the mean performance scores of SS 2 students taught Electrolysis using three pair strategy and those taught using discussion method. This was in favour of experimental group.

Table 4: ANCOVA test on significant difference between the mean retention scores of SS 2 students taught Electrolysis using three pair strategy and those taught using discussion method.

(Effects of Three-Pair-Strategy using VARK Model on Performance ... Abdulmalik, L., Et. al. 2025)

Source	Type III sum of square	D.F	Mean square	F	Sig
Corrected model	1268.389	2	634.194	40.306	.000
Intercept	1528.879	1	1528.879	79.167	.000
Retention	107.797	1	107.460	6.830	.011
Treat ment	618.797	1	618.797	39.327	.000
Error	1038.481	69	15.735		
Total	45582.00	71			
Corrected total	2306.870	70			

Table 4 shows that the p-value of 0.000 is less than that the alpha level of 0.05 with 70 degree of freedom ($0.00 < 0.05$, df 70). This means that the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the mean retention scores of SS 2 taught Electrolysis using three pair strategy and those taught using discussion method. in favour of experimental group.

Discussion

The findings revealed that the mean performance scores of students taught using three pair instructional strategy performed higher than those taught using the discussion method. This finding agreed with that of Johnson and Johnson (2009) noted that students who used the three pair strategy showed significant gains in achievement and engagement compared to those who used traditional teaching methods, Similarly, the study was in line with the study of Danladi (2010) that jigsaw instructional strategy has significant effect on students' achievement in senior secondary school biology contents. This means that students achieved meaningfully in biology as a result of the Jigsaw teaching method and that the method was adequate for the instruction process.

The result from hypothesis testing revealed that there is significant difference in the mean performance scores of SS 2 students taught Electrolysis using three pair strategy and those taught using the discussion, Method. This was in favour of experimental group. This finding was in line with the finding of Danladi (2010) that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of biology teachers taught using jigsaw instructional strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching method. This finding also supported the finding of Adejoh (2015) that the use of jigsaw instructional strategy and conventional teaching method for teaching social studies in junior secondary schools when compared to the conventional teaching method is significantly different. Invariably, these findings show the effectiveness of three pair strategy as a method for enhancing academic performance regardless of the subject matter and level of class.

The findings from results revealed that the mean retention scores of students taught with three pair strategy is higher than those taught using the discussion method. This finding supported the finding of Gubbad (2010) that co-operative learning on students' retention of 6th grade primary school pupils in mathematics concept is higher than those taught using conventional teaching method. Similarly, this finding agreed with the finding of Lawan (2016) that there was significant difference between the

(Effects of Three-Pair-Strategy using VARK Model on Performance ... Abdulmalik, L., Et. al. 2025)

mean retention scores of students taught mensuration concepts using jigsaw II co-operative learning strategy and those taught using conventional lecture method in favour of the Jigsaw II co-operative learning strategy.

Conclusion

This study showed that the three pair instructional strategy helped to improve students' academic performance and retention in electrolysis than students taught using the discussion method. In fact, three pair instructional strategy has demonstrated its effectiveness in increasing meaningful learning in chemistry because it is an activity-oriented method which allowed individual learner to participate actively according to their assigning roles, involved checking and assessing individual academic confidence.

Recommendation

It is therefore Recommended that;

- i. both Federal and State levels of education teachers should adopt three pair instructional strategy because it boosts the participation of students in chemistry thereby improving the academic performance and retention of students in Electrolysis concept,
- ii. Zamfara State Ministry of Education should organized Seminary, Workshops and Conferences for Teachers most especially Chemistry Teachers on how to uses three pair strategy in teaching electrolysis.

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